

Process Analysis through Length Consistency

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Abstract : The requirement for consistency in Physics allows one to find a common ground between disciplines such that their fundamental equations share a common parameter set and mathematical method for equation extraction. In this paper we concentrate on Relativity and Quantum Mechanics with the primary goal of determining something of the structure of the gravitational constant. The analysis will be seen to be very straightforward, primarily classical in nature using linear algebra concepts, yet deriving an estimate of the value of the constant along with dependencies never before known.

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